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Teacher Performance Model In Pandemic Times Based on Emotional Intelligence Mediated And Moderated By Transformational Leadership (Study of Jabodetabek Teacher)

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Abstract

The examine proposes and tests performance research models influenced by emotional intelligence as well as mediated and moderated by transformational leadership. Coronavirus that has a global impact, very influential to the world of education. Especially in Indonesia, covid19 greatly affects the teaching and learning process, students learn with online systems, they learn from home, these conditions make teachers have to make sure the students understand the learning obtained. In addition, the emotional intelligence condition of teachers is also expected to play a role in maintaining work life balance between work and family. This study evaluated the relationship of the model using PLS through modelling of SEM structural equations through questionnaires given to 211 Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi) teachers. The effects of the information analysis showed that emotional intelligence had a advantageous effect on teacher performance. The analysis indicated that emotional intelligence comprise a positive effect on transformational leadership. Information analysis shows that transformational leadership has no positive impact on performance. The information analysis showed that emotional intelligence had no a critical effect on the performance moderated by transformational leadership. Analysis the information revealed that emotional intelligence had no a significant effect on the performance moderated by transformational leadership. This study can be useful to enrich the scientific insights of management, especially related to the application and development of performance concepts.

Kata kunci: *Performance, Emotional intelligence, Work Life Balance*

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BACKGROUND

Coronavirus has affected daily life and impacted the global economy. In controlling the spread of covid19, various countries in the world implement a lockdown system. Covid19 has a major impact on trade, tourism industry, pharmaceutical industry, education and other industries and also has an impact on other movements in the world. The impact of covid19 on the economy includes disrupting production supply chains, production of goods being slow, most nations encountering misfortunes in national and worldwide commerce, and slow moving income development (Haleem et al., 2020). According to a UNESCO report, for the world of education, the coronavirus has affected 90% of the overall student population within the world during mid-April 2020 and has decreased by 67% since June 2020. As a result, the big impact of covid19 is experienced by all students in the world (Jena, 2020).

(Onyema, 2020) In the United States, schools are generally closed and exam schedules are canceled. New York and California are among the states that have been heavily affected by the coronavirus. School closures within the U.S. affect more than 60 million understudies within the nation. In Spain, approximately 11 million understudies have been influenced by school closures due to the spread of the coronavirus. The closure of the school driven to the suspension of business contracts for representatives who worked at the school. In Saudi Arabia, it detailed that schools and colleges were requested to close and directed to run virtual schools so that, education process could continue effectively, efficiently and qualifiedly.

The condition of the covid 19 pandemic in Indonesia is still high. Here is a table of provinces that run PPKM emergency period, from July 3 to July 20, 2021, namely Banten, Bali, West Java, Jakarta, Central Java, East Java. A total of 77.5% of additional corona cases in Indonesia are sourced from the province. With the outbreak of covid cases in Indonesia, it certainly also has an impact on other sectors such as education, tourism, and business.

Figure 1: Province Run PPKM Emergency
Source: databoks.katadata.co.id

Most countries in the world apply restrictions on movement in their communities such as lockdown, social distancing, and wearing masks when out of the house. Teachers teach online from home, but of course there are various problems with implementing this working home including inadequate work equipment and equipment at home, lack of concentration on every worker when working at home, and also work family conflict. Most teachers feel pressured by the case of covid 19, so it takes a motivation drive sourced from the leadership, namely in this case the principal to improve employee morale, so that teachers do not feel stressed because of their work.

With the transition of online learning since the outbreak of the coronavirus, there has been a change in the process of learning and teaching activities in the world of education, especially in schools. This can be seen as an organizational change that can be frustrating and stressful and face uncertainty and uncertainty. The implementation and use of technology-based learning is a process that requires the knowledge and skills of every teacher. In addition, cooperation between students and parents is needed in order to implement teaching to be in accordance with online learning, so that transformational leadership effectiveness is needed in school success during this corona19.

(Ugc & Group, 2013) stated that the covid 19 pandemic makes employees emotionally unbalanced, they do all activities at home, be it household chores or office work. That is, physically they are at home, but mentally they do office work. This can lead to disruption of emotional attachment to family. And of course it also interferes with emotional bonding with work. Emotional intelligence is an important factor in the organization, as it will help employees to manage stress and control emotions, as well as ensure good performance. This condition also occurs in the world of education, all run online by teachers and students, so they run from their homes, so that the role of emotional intelligence is needed in the management of stress, identifying emotional roots and having empathy during covid19 so that the teaching of emotional intelligence can be implemented so that it has important meaning in the learning process during the pandemic (Balamurugan & Prabakaran, 2019).

LITERATURE RIEW**Covid 19**

(Chanana & Sangeeta, 2020) recently appeared in Wuhan, China a respiratory disease known as covid19. At least this global pandemic has confirmed about 5 million cases of death according to who in May 2020. Everyone infected with the covid19 virus according to WHO will experience different symptoms and can recover. Seniors and individuals who have a medical history such as diabetes, cancer, and other chronic diseases may experience severe conditions. So who warns that every individual can protect themselves by washing their hands.

Performance

Performance is described as an overview of the effectiveness of activities so that the achievement of goals and the success of the work is realized. Performance is the quantitative and subjective expression of the group or business that accomplishes the work in achieving work objectives (Bass, 2008). Performance is a concept that describes a person using one's potential through knowledge, skills and enabling oneself to achieve one's own goals and expectations. (Yıldız et al., 2008). The reason of execution assessment is to move forward worker performance so that they can take organizational decisions related to wages, promotions, dismissals in accordance with performance results. So that the organization needs to recognize all staff and be able to distinguish failed staff and successful staff.

Performance is a multicomponent concept and basically consists of various aspects, namely the role of one's behavior from the results achieved (Borman et al., 2014). Behavior can be seen from a person's actions so that the work can be completed, while the aspect of the results is a consequence of individual work behavior (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015).

(Okoth & Florah, 2019) Employee performance is the foremost critical subordinate variable in brain research and organizational. Performance is basic to the victory of the organization. Performance is described as a progressive process for improving individual work by being aligned between actual performance and organizational strategic goals (Cole, 2011). Performance is multidimensional, can take the form of task performance, adaptive performance and also contextual performance.

Transformational leadership

Transformational leadership alludes to the approach of persuading their supporters to distinguish organizational objectives and interface. Transformational leadership roles are critical in achieving effective management change (Kim, 2014). Transformational leadership comprise of four measurements, specifically idealized impact, uplifting inspirational, mental incitement, individual consideration (Bass, 2008). It can be made clear that the ideal influence, otherwise known as charisma, is a leader who exhibits moral behavior and upholds ethics. Inspirational motivation involves followers who can provide energy by articulating a motivating vision. Transformational leaders can motivate workers to share their vision and engage workers to attain that vision. Intellectual stimulation refers to leaders who encourage employee creativity, present new ideas that are challenging and have different ways of solving problems. Ultimately, individual consideration involves paying attention to the individual's need to excel and providing coaching and mentoring.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is an interesting topic and is very helpful in understanding within the area of organizational behaviour, management, and also helps in human relations in the workplace (Gottman et al., 1998). It has been found that emotions have a direct impact on human relationships, so emotions should be considered in managing relationships with others (Hopkins & Yonker, 2015).

The conceptualization of emotional intelligence began in the 1920s when Thorndike classified the concept into three measurements: mechanical insights, abstract intelligence and social insight. Emotional intelligence was first introduced by (Mayer, John; Salovey, 2004) as an ability to measure and show emotions, deal with emotions, utilize emotions when solving problems. (Mayer et al., 2008) defines emotional intelligence as an individual's competence to identify and show emotions to facilitate judgment. (Mayer, John; Salovey, 2004) states that emotional intelligence includes three domains namely, emotional intelligence is considered as a set of interconnected mental capacities for the utilize of emotional information, second, emotional

intelligence is treated as a set of traits to adjust and survive and the third emotional intelligence is self-contained on the basis of behavioral competence that combines ability, affective and cognitive (Boyatzis & Boyatzis, 2008).

INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VARIABLES

1. Emotional intelligence has a positive influence on teacher performance

Emotional intelligence is a potential factor in achieving individual performance at work. (Burnett et al., 2010) point out that emotional intelligence can lead to different success rates. Because emotional intelligence source of inspiration, information, input, innovation and effectiveness. According to (Goleman, 2017) emotional intelligence is one of the main factors for adaption, succeed, and performance.

2. Emotional intelligence has a positive influence on transformational leadership

Although there is debate in the literature about the construction of emotional intelligence for leadership (Antonakis, 2009) argues that an idea that has many relational aspects in an activity, more and more emotional intelligence will be needed by individuals in one place. Thus, leaders who have the ability to understand employee emotions will understand the consequences of his actions against others so that they most likely have to provide more effective leadership (Day & Carroll, 2004). According to (Harms & Credé, 2010) emotional intelligence and transformational leadership are linked.

3. Transformational leadership has a positive influence on teacher performance

Some researchers have the opinion that transformational leadership has a decrease affect compared to transactional leadership styles over performance (Sparks & Schenk, 2001). Other studies have described transformational leadership styles as having a greater impact on individual performance than transactional leadership styles ((Kalsoom et al., 2018).

4. Emotional intelligence includes a positive influence on teacher performance mediated by transformational leadership

Research shows that emotional intelligence has an effect on transformational leadership (Barling et al., 2000). Palmer (2001) found a noteworthy relationship between emotional intelligence and few transformational leadership model factors. (Avolio & Gardner, 2005) shows that emotional intelligence leaders make up the majority in transformational leadership. The implication of emotional intelligence on employee performance is clarified in (Gadaf Rexhepi, 2017) that in Macedonia success in overseeing a change is largely determined by the level of emotional intelligence obtained. Emotional intelligence research findings have a positive effect on the auditor's performance. Similarly, obtained by (Jaya et al., 2017) stated that emotional intelligence has a significance effect on performance.

5. Emotional Intelligence positively impacts teacher performance moderated by Transformational Leadership

According to (Jafri et al., 2016) if a person has high emotional intelligence then one also has a better ability to understand personal emotions and others. Emotional intelligence can create positive things in the work environment, get good relationships with colleagues and be able to improve performance. Then, (Khalili, 2017) states that emotional intelligence underlies a leader's ability to motivate and inspire (Lindebaum & Cartwright, 2010) argues that emotional intelligence and transformational leadership can improve when combined with experience, personality, ability and innovation. And there are various studies that show that transformational leadership that has a good relationship with employees can encourage the creation of a good employee performance climate. Empirical evidence suggests that transformational leadership can moderate the correlation among emotional intelligence and performance (Lindebaum & Cartwright, 2010).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH HYPHOTHESIS

After describing the description of the problem formulation, the next step is to explain about the formulation of the research hypothesis, namely:

1. Emotional Intelligence positively effect on teacher performance
2. Emotional Intelligence positively effect transformational leadership
3. Transformational leadership positively effect teacher performance
4. Emotional Intelligence positively effect on teacher performance mediated by Transformational leadership
5. Emotional Intelligence positively effect on teacher performance in transformational leadership moderation

3RESEARCH METHODE

This research has a quantitative research design with an explanatory method approach. The teacher was the subject of a study of 211, with objects in the areas of Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi (Jabodetabek).

RESEARCH RESULT

SEM-PLS (PLS) analysis

Outer Model Evaluation

a. Convergent Validity

To evaluate the research model is done through loading factor assessment. If the loading factor number is above 0.7 then the observed variable is valid (Hair et al, 2017a). Loading factor values can be observed from each variable.

Source: Information Preparing (2021)
Figure 3. Loading Factor Value Diagram Outer Model Evaluation

Table 1 Evaluation Convergent Validity

	Construct	Loading Factor	Criteria (Loading Factor ≥ 0.6)
	Convergent Validity (Outer Loadings)	EI1 <- Emotional intelligence	0,740
EI10 <- Emotional intelligence		0,745	Valid
EI2 <- Emotional intelligence		0,735	Valid
EI3 <- Emotional intelligence		0,851	Valid
EI4 <- Emotional intelligence		0,777	Valid
EI5 <- Emotional intelligence		0,725	Valid
EI6 <- Emotional intelligence		0,710	Valid
EI7 <- Emotional intelligence		0,802	Valid
EI8 <- Emotional intelligence		0,653	Valid
EI9 <- Emotional intelligence		0,669	Valid
Emotional intelligence *Transformational leadership <- M – Transformational leadership		2,234	Valid
LEAD1 <- Transformational leadership		0,822	Valid
LEAD10 <- Transformational leadership		0,619	Valid
LEAD2 <- Transformational leadership		0,834	Valid
LEAD3 <- Transformational leadership		0,847	Valid
LEAD4 <- Transformational leadership		0,864	Valid
LEAD5 <- Transformational leadership		0,853	Valid
LEAD6 <- Transformational leadership		0,782	Valid
LEAD7 <- Transformational leadership		0,854	Valid
LEAD8 <- Transformational leadership		0,820	Valid
LEAD9 <- Transformational leadership		0,765	Valid
PER1 <- Performance		0,827	Valid
PER2 <- Performance		0,805	Valid
PER3 <- Performance		0,660	Valid
PER4 <- Performance		0,809	Valid
PER5 <- Performance		0,771	Valid
PER6 <- Performance		0,824	Valid
PER7 <- Performance		0,665	Valid
PER8 <- Performance		0,802	Valid
PER8 <- Performance		0,802	Valid

Source: Information Preparing (2021)

Figure 3 and Table 1 explain that the loading factor of each variable > 0.6 , so that the variable can be used in the model.

Furthermore, the normal fluctuation extricated (AVE) to focuses to energize reinforce the comes about of concurrent validity with criteria in the event that the AVE esteem > 0.5 develop in this consider is said to be valid (Hair et al, 2019). The taking after are displayed the comes of the normal fluctuation extricated test utilizing the PLS 3.0 program:

Table 2 Check Extracted Average Variance

Latent	(AVE)	R Critical	Criteria (AVE $\geq$ 0.5)
<i>Emotional intelligence</i>	0,552	0,5	Valid
Transformational leadership	0,654	0,5	Valid
Performance	0,598	0,5	Valid
M – Transformational leadership	1,000	0,5	Valid

Source: Information Preparing (2021)

Table 2 results in all latent variables obtaining AVE values more prominent that 0.5. Encourage, it can be tried.

Discriminant Validity Test

The results of the cross loading test are shown in the table below.

Table 3 Test Values of Discriminant Cross Loading Validity Test

	Emotional intelligence	Transformational leadership	Performance	M – Transformational leadership
EI1	0,740	0,595	0,615	-0,432
EI10	0,745	0,567	0,654	-0,332
EI2	0,735	0,597	0,627	-0,413
EI3	0,851	0,677	0,785	-0,479
EI4	0,777	0,561	0,589	-0,453
EI5	0,725	0,531	0,614	-0,401
EI6	0,710	0,513	0,525	-0,354
EI7	0,802	0,614	0,729	-0,515
EI8	0,653	0,478	0,535	-0,369
EI9	0,669	0,578	0,558	-0,263
EI * KT	-0,544	-0,561	-0,542	1,000
LEAD1	0,663	0,822	0,557	-0,464
LEAD10	0,493	0,619	0,414	-0,351
LEAD2	0,674	0,834	0,603	-0,494
LEAD3	0,644	0,847	0,574	-0,504
LEAD4	0,684	0,864	0,599	-0,532
LEAD5	0,690	0,853	0,648	-0,535
LEAD6	0,552	0,782	0,517	-0,409
LEAD7	0,662	0,854	0,584	-0,469
LEAD8	0,602	0,820	0,537	-0,376
LEAD9	0,546	0,765	0,472	-0,358
PER1	0,682	0,495	0,827	-0,351
PER2	0,651	0,512	0,805	-0,515
PER3	0,568	0,444	0,660	-0,546
PER4	0,686	0,586	0,809	-0,364
PER5	0,685	0,558	0,771	-0,417
PER6	0,679	0,568	0,824	-0,405

PER7	0,574	0,476	0,665	-0,305
PER8	0,692	0,587	0,802	-0,464

Source: Data Processing (2021)

Table 3 explains that the overall indicator contains a high relationship to its develop compared to other builds. So the conclusion that the examine appear gotten great discriminant validity on discriminant validity with cross loading.

Reliability Test

Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability values greater than 0.70 indicate that a construct is dependable (Hair et al, 2017). Table 4.4 shows the results of the construct reliability check.

Table 4. Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability

Latent	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Emotional intelligence	0,909	0,924
Transformational leadership	0,940	0,949
Performance	0,902	0,922
M – Transformational leadership	1,000	1,000

Table 4 outlines that latent constructs have good reliability because they are more than 0.7. So that the next stage of testing can be done.

Inner Model Testing

The inner test of the model is useful for knowing the significance between independent variables with dependent variables and to find out how much influence the variables have, the test comes about can be seen in figure 4

Figure 4. Structural Model

Figure 4 obtains a t-statistical value of > 1.96, it can be said that the indicator has a positive and significant impact. Further testing of the inner model includes R-square, f-square, and Predictive Relevance (Q Square Value).

a. R-Square

In the following table there is an explanation of R-square, Chin (1998) in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011: 21) states that if the value of R-square 0.75 is obtained then the model is strong, if the result is 0.50 then the model is concluded moderate, if the result is 0.25 then it is stated that the model is weak. Based on the comes of the test, R-square are gotten as takes after.

Table 5 R Square

	R Square	Strong Relationship
Transformational leadership	0,597	Moderate
Performance	0,726	Moderate

Table 5 describes transformational leadership variables having an R Square value of 0.597 which means emotional intelligence contributes an influence of 0.597 or 59.7% to transformational leadership. The remaining 40.3% was gotten from the impact of other factors that were not observed.

Performance variables have an R-Square of 0.726 which states that emotional intelligence mediated by transformational leadership has an influence contribution of 0.726 or 72.6% to performance. A value of 27.4% was derived from the influence of other variables that were not watched.

b. f-Square

According to Ghozali and Latan (2015:81), f Square points are used to determine the structural influence of latent variable predictors. If the result of the value f Square 0.02 then it means that the result is small, the effect size of 0.15 shows that the effect of the intermediate assessment, and the effect size is worth 0.35 shows that the valuation is of great value (Cohen, 1988 in Yamin and Kurniawan, 2011: 21). Based on the test results, f-Square comes about are gotten as takes after.

f-Square Table 6

Variable	Effect Size	Rating
Transformational leadership		
<i>Emotional intelligence</i>	1,481	Big
Performance		
<i>Emotional intelligence</i>	0,801	Big
Transformational leadership	0,002	Small
M- Transformational leadership	0,027	Small

Source: Information Preparing (2021)

That variable appears in Table 6 Emotional intelligence encompasses a broad range of influences on transformational leadership. The variables of emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, and M-transformational leadership have influence with categories that fall into categories large, small and small in influencing performance.

c. Q² Predictive Relevance

The following organize is Q square prescient pertinence on the build show. Qsquare testing contains a estimation work against the perception values produced by the demonstrate and its parameters. According to Cohen in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011:21), if case the esteem of Q-square > 0 at the poin it is said that the demonstate has presient significance esteem. Though in case Q-square < 0 then it is said that the model lacks predictive relevance. In table 7 can be seen Q Suare predictive relevance.

Table 7 Q² Predictive Relevance

Variable	R Square	1-R Square
Transformational leadership	0,597	0,403

Performance	0,726	0,274
$Q^2 =$	$Q^2 = 1 - (1-R_1^2) (1-R_2^2) = 0,890$	
Galat =	$Q^2 = 100\% - 89,0\% = 11,0\%$	

Source: Information Preparing (2021)

In the event that the Q Square esteem is more noteworthy than 0, at that poin it is said the demonstate is communicated to have prescient signigance. The Q square esteem points to devcide the impact of auxiliary models on endogenous idle factors. This is where 0.890 or 89.0% has a relative influence on endogenous latent variables, the remaining 11.0% is model error.

d. Hypothesis Testing

According to Kock, N. (2016), path coefficient and t-value values are obtained to assess significance and prediction in hypothesis testing. The following are the criteria for testing the research hypothesis:

- The t-statistical esteem > 1.96 (utilized for coordinate impact), or ρ -value < 0.05 then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is acknowledged. - The t-statistical esteem < 1.96 (utilized for coordinate impact), or p -value > 0.05 then H_0 is acknowledged and H_1 is rejected.

1. Hypothesis 1: Emotional intelligence effect on teacher performance

Hypothesis 1: emotional intelligence has a significance effect on performance. This hypothesis was developed into the following statistical hypothesis:

H_0 : Emotional intelligence does not have a significance effect on teacher performance;

H_1 : Emotional intelligence has a significance effect on teacher performance.

Moreover, based totally at the above hypothesis, the hypothesis was tested using the bootstrapping method with SmartPLS software, and obtained the following values:

Table 8 Path coefficients and t-calculate the effect of emotional intelligence on teacher performance

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistik	p-value	Conclusion
The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Performance	0,755	7,067	0,000	Reject H_0

Source: Information Preparing (2021)

The direction of influence of emotional intelligence on performance is positive, meaning that if emotional intelligence is superior, the performance variable will improve or increase, according to the results of table 4.8 above the original sample (o) esteem of 0.755. The effect of emotional intelligence on overall performance is significance, as evidenced by the value of t-statistics which is 7.067 more than t table or $7,067 > 1.96$, and the value of p value of 0.000 is lower than alpha 5% (0.05). As a result, H_2 is accepted implying that emotional intelligence has a significance effect on performance. This finding is in consistent with recent studies (Bozionelos & Singh, 2017; Darvishmotevali et al., 2018) which found that emotional intelligence has a positive effect on teacher performance.

2. Hypothesis 2: The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Transformational Leadership

Hypothesis 2: Emotional intelligence has a significance effect on transformational leadership. And it was from the hypothesis developed into the following statistical hypothesis:

H_0 : Emotional intelligence does not have a significance effect on transformational leadership;

H_2 : Emotional intelligence has a significance effect on transformational leadership.

Furthermore, the hypothesis was tested using the bootstrapping approach with SmartPLS software, and the following values were obtained.

Table 9 Path coefficients and t-calculates the Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Transformational Leadership

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistik	p-value	Conclusion
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The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Transformational Leadership	0,773	13,193	0,000	Reject H ₀
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Source: Information Preparing (2021)

From comes about of Table 9 the value (O) of 0.773 clarifies that the course of impact of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership is positive or unidirectional, meaning that if emotional intelligence is superior than transformational leadership will increase or get better. The influence of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership yielded significant results, the t-statistical value was 13,193 more than the table t or $13,193 > 1.96$, and the p value of 0.000 was less than the alpha 5% (0.05). As a result, H₁ is accepted to mean that emotional intelligence has a significance influence on transformational leadership. This finding is consistent with previous research (Potter et al., 2018; Rinfret et al., 2020) that shows emotional intelligence has a significance effect on transformational leadership.

3. Hypothesis 3: The effect of transformational leadership on teacher performance

Hypothesis 3: Transformational leadership has a significant impact on teacher performance. This hypothesis was later developed into a statistical hypothesis, which is as follows:

H₀: Transformational leadership does not have a significant impact on teacher performance;

H₃: Transformational leadership has a significant impact on teacher performance.

Table 10 Path coefficients and t-calculate the effect of transformational leadership on teacher performance

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistik	p-value	Conclusion
The Impact of Transformational Leadership on Performance	0,043	0,441	0,659	Accept H ₀

Source: Information Preparing (2021)

Table 10 obtaining an Original Sample (O) of 0.043 indicates that the direction of influence from transformational leadership to performance is positive or unidirectional, implying that if transformational leadership is superior than performance will increase or get better. The effect of transformational leadership on performance is insignificant, with a t-statistical value of 0.441 less than a table t or $0.441 < 1.96$, and a p value of 0.659 greater than alpha 5% (0.05). As a result, H₃ is rejected meaning transformational leadership has not a significance effect on performance. This study disagrees with (Ng, 2017; Soane et al., 2015) that have the result that transformational leadership has a significance effect on teacher performance.

4. Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Performance by mediated Transformational Leadership

Hypothesis 4: emotional intelligence has a significance effect on performance by mediating transformational leadership. This hypothesis was developed into a statistical hypothesis that is:

H₀: Emotional Intelligence does not have a significance effect on performance by mediated transformational leadership;

H₄: Emotional Intelligence has a significance effect on performance by mediating transformational leadership.

Furthermore, based on the above hypothesis tested the hypothesis by bootstrapping method using SmartPLS software, and obtained values, namely:

Table 11 Pathway coefficients and t-calculate the effect of Emotional Intelligence on Performance by mediated Transformational Leadership

	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistik	p-value	Conclusion
Emotional Intelligence on Performance by	0,033	0,429	0,668	Accept H ₀

<i>Mediated Transformational Leadership</i>				
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Source: Information Preparing (2021)

Table 11 yield an Original Sample (O) value of 0.033 indicating that the impact of emotional intelligence on performance by mediating transformational leadership is negative or unidirectional, implying that if emotional intelligence will cause transformational leadership the way better that will further improve or better performance. The effect of emotional intelligence on performance by mediated transformational leadership is insignificant, the t-statistical value of 0.429 is less than the table t or $0.429 < 1.96$, and the p value of $0.668 > \alpha 5\%$ (0.05). Thus H_1 is rejected indicating that emotional intelligence does not have a critical impact on performance mediated by transformational leadership. This study agrees with (Cavazotte et al., 2012) which states that emotional intelligence has no critical impact on performance mediated by transformational leadership.

5. Effect of M - Transformational Leadership on teacher Performance

Hypothesis 5: M - Transformational leadership has a significance effect on teacher performance. Furthermore, this hypothesis was developed into the following statistical hypothesis:
 H_0 :M - Transformational leadership has no significance effect on teacher performance;
 H_5 :M - Transformational leadership has a significance effect on teacher performance.

Table 12 Path coefficients and t-calculates the Effect of M - Transformational leadership on Performance

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>t-Statistik</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Conclusion
M – Transformational leadership to Performance	-0,048	1,343	0,179	Accept H_0

Source: Information Preparing (2021)

From the comes about of table 12 gotten an Original Sample (O) value of -0.048 this shows the course of impact of M - transformational leadership on teacher performance is negative or opposite, meaning that if M - transformational leadership increases or the superior than performance will decrease or get worse. The effect of M - transformational leadership to performance is significant, the t-statistical value of 1.343 is smaller than the table t or $1,343 < 1.96$, and the p value of 0.179 is greater than the alpha 5% (0.05), hence H_4 is rejected meaning M - Transformational leadership has no significant affect on performance. The results of this study agree with (Alfonsina, 2019) who stated that transformational M-leadership has no significant effect on teacher performance.

CONCLUSION

The following are the findings of this research:

1. Emotional intelligence has a significance effect on teacher performance.
2. Emotional intelligence has a significance effect on transformational leadership.
3. Transformational leadership has no significance effect on teacher performance.
- 4.M - Transformational leadership has no significance effect on teacher performance.
5. Emotional Intelligence does not have a significance effect on the teacher performance mediated transformational leadership.

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